

The Necessity To Defend Against Manoeuvre Warfare In The Competition With China

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Author: Dr. Dipl.-Kfm. Wolfgang Müller; Research Interests: Total Defense, China, Weaponization of Economics. The views contained in this article are the author's alone and do not represent the views of the German Institute for Defense and Strategic Studies. The views contained in this article are the author's alone and do not represent the views of the German Institute for Defense and Strategic Studies or the German Armed Forces.

Abstract: China's weaponisation of economics is fully in line with China's grand strategy. China relies mainly on using the indirect instead of the direct approach. Manoeuvre warfare as an indirect approach sees the opponent as an interconnected system, to which measures against identified vulnerabilities are applied. The goal is systemic destruction – the incapacitation or collapse of the opponent's whole system – rather than cumulative destruction through a series of attritional engagements. An authoritarian government, like China, with unified, centralised and nearly unlimited state power exercise economic coercion through state capitalism against states, which rely on the private sector and an international, integrated global supply chain system for their economic welfare, using speed, agility and simultaneity.

Problem statement: Is the weaponisation of economics part of the competition with the People's Republic of China?

Bottom-line-up-front: Manoeuvre warfare (or the indirect approach) is not dead, but it has to adjust to be able not only to counter attritional warfare (or the direct approach) but also an opponent using the indirect approach itself.

So what?: We have to take the tools, features and endowments of coercive economic measures being applied by an authoritarian power towards liberal democracies to draw conclusions, what kind of deterrence and defence liberal democracies can muster to counter the threat.

The PRC's Grand Strategy

The People's Republic of China (PRC) has a distinct understanding of what a Grand Strategy is and what kind of Grand Strategy the PRC defines as its own. The PRC has to be considered more and more a systemic rival.[1] It is therefore important not only to understand what fields are being considered as parts of the PRC's Grand Strategy but also to understand the Strategic Culture of the PRC. The Strategic Culture is essential to be able to define what kind of approach the PRC is using in its current grey zone activities as the "awkward and uncomfortable space between traditional conceptions of war and peace".[2] Those activities can be conducted in two ways, following the dichotomy of the direct or indirect approach,[3] respectively, the attritional or manoeuvral approach.[4] In the application of either the direct or indirect approach in economics, the specific features of authoritarian regimes versus liberal democracies and their respective economic models have to be considered. Finally, examples of how the weaponisation of economics is taken place and what potential avenues are to be explored as counterstrategies are provided.

The PRC's Grand Strategy and its implication for the use of economics

The definition of Grand Strategy in this paper is a broad and functional one; its role is to coordinate and direct all-disparate-resources of the nation (political, economic, technological and military) towards the attainment of a national objective.[5] In the PRC, it is understood as the "technique of national strategic management".[6] It differs in two distinct ways from the more westernised definition: First of all, the instruments being used are not confined to the resources mentioned above, but include all the elements of comprehensive national strength.[7] This broader understanding got somehow lost in Western

strategic thinking because it was already introduced very early through the term “political warfare”.[8] Secondly, the national objective of the PRC refers both to national security and national development, so it is applicable both in peace- and wartime and serves equally as an orientation for domestic and foreign affairs.[9] This distinction, especially the second, is important for further understanding the application of the Chinese Grand Strategy.

As the Grand Strategy serves to attain the national interest, it is important to be clear about the PRC’s core national interests – they are: “to maintain China’s fundamental system and state security; state sovereignty and territorial integrity; and the continued stable development of the economy and society”.[10] This leads to the conclusion, that “it is necessary to uphold a holistic view of national security, balance internal and external security, homeland and citizen security, traditional and nontraditional security, subsistence and development security, and China’s own security and the common security of the world.”[11]

One Major Determinant of the Grand Strategy

The foundation for the Grand Strategy is rooted in the Strategic Culture. The PRC considers Confucianism to be the determining factor in its own strategic thinking.[12] The Confucian concept of the *da tong* (typically called the “great harmony”) asks for harmony over conflict.[13] Considering the influence of Sun Tsu’s “Art of War”, [14] the Chinese self-perception is that it has always preferred defence over offence.[15] It is, therefore, stated in official documents as such.[16] The term “Cult of Defence” was introduced to describe this cornerstone of self-perceived Chinese strategic thinking.[17] On the other hand, by analysing the wars the PRC was involved, the result looks much more contradictory to the self-perceived image: The PRC was quite willing to use force over time, influenced by realpolitik,[18] therefore it can be stated that “China’s leaders never seem to have seen a war they didn’t like.”[19] The term “offensive realism” is may be best suited for a summarising description.[20] The PRC’s military strategy, “Active Defence”, [21] can be seen as a combination of both understandings: “It can be proposed that the official thinking ... fit into the ‘duality’ culture scheme..., with the strong, peaceful rhetoric and non-conflict preference, but increasingly assertive behaviour and pro-active stance when dealing with national (core) interests...”. [22]

It will be necessary to clarify in what domains “Active Defence” is taking place. There is a rich pool of official and semi-official sources available for this. In the often-mentioned book “Unrestricted Warfare”, it is stated: “If we acknowledge that the new principles of war are no longer using armed force to compel the enemy to submit to one’s will”, but rather are “using all means, including armed force or

non-armed force, military and non-military, and lethal and non-lethal means to compel the enemy to accept one's interests." [23] Although there are strong critics about the book as not being authoritative, [24] it was still published at the "PLA Literature and Arts Publishing House" and very likely with the consent of higher authorities – acknowledging the restrictions service members face when publishing work-related matters without permission. However, there are references to applying this kind of warfare in Chinese official documents. [25] As we focus on the domain of economics, it can be concluded: "The default behaviour and culture of the U.S. foreign policy community is to approach the economic domain mainly through the lens of competition, whereas the Chinese Communist Party's organisational culture views the economic component of foreign policy through the lens of warfare." [26]

The Indirect Approach as the Means of Choice

As the spheres of engagement are defined, it remains to outline how these engagements are being executed. The Strategic Culture is, as outlined, a main factor. Shortly after the publication of the aforementioned book "Unrestricted Warfare", the Chinese Communist Party Central Committee and the Central Military Commission approved the concept of the "Three Warfares" in 2003. [27] It was integrated into the "Guidelines for the Political Work of the People's Liberation Army". [28] In an analysis of this concept, it was remarked: [29] "The "Three Warfares" is a concept that spans the war/peace divide, operating throughout the continuum of international rivalry. ... there are few fixed patterns in Chinese strategy, and this is deliberate. How Beijing puts principles into practice will vary widely from circumstance to circumstance, confounding efforts at prediction. ... the doctrine is entirely congruent with Chinese strategic culture, as well as with the universal logic of strategy." [30] This concept also leads to the conclusion that "violence may be used as the final blow to knock out an enemy after it has been relentlessly sapped, subdued, and undermined from within." [31] It also allows the interpretation that decisive manoeuvres can finish the conflict quickly to avoid a longer attritional engagement and limit the conflict's size. [32]

Chinese Grand Strategy must, therefore, be understood as the national strategic management of all elements of comprehensive national strength. It determines both the foreign and domestic agenda, as the core national interests encompass international and national elements. The PRC will actively engage, if deemed necessary, in war and non-war-spheres if core national interests are being threatened. The PRC is already applying grey zone activities [33] and the weaponisation of economics prior to (sub-threshold) or part of a direct conflict is fully in line with the PRC's Grand Strategy, as it is closely

interlinked with the national development/well-being and hence with the survival of the communist party rule. In doing so, the PRC will refer to defensive offensives (and therefore preemptive strikes or self-defence counterattacks)[34] and will prefer the indirect over the attritional approach: “When it comes to ‘wars of choice’, though, the fact remains that the Chinese have traditionally favoured the indirect approach.”[35]

The Characteristics of an Indirect Approach Used by an Authoritarian Regime

To deepen the analysis of economic warfare through an indirect approach, a closer look at the fundamentals of the indirect approach is necessary:[36] The indirect approach views the opponent as an interconnected system to which measures against identified vulnerabilities are applied. The aim is to undermine the will and weaken the cohesion of the opponent’s system by defeating critical capabilities, as well as to set conditions and create opportunities to bring one’s own strengths to bear. It focuses on restricting options available to the opponent, preserving the maximum range of one’s own actions. It is subtler, and plausible deniability is easier to achieve. The core characteristics are a) speed, b) agility and c) simultaneity. These actions should ultimately lead to disruption, disorder (physical, functional, temporal and moral) and paralysis on the opponent’s side: The goal of manoeuvre warfare is systemic destruction—the incapacitation or collapse of the opponent’s whole eco-system (state, economy and society) – rather than cumulative destruction through a series of attritional engagements. This follows the logic of creating synergies: weakening one system in the interconnected ecosystem of the opponent will create a synergetic effect on the functioning of another system.[37]

In executing this strategy, the PRC, with its authoritarian regime and the application of state-capitalism, has advantages in speed, agility, and simultaneity over liberal democracies.[38] The decision-making is faster, as power in authoritarian states is centralised in the hands of a single leader or a small group of elites. There is no need for an extensive debate, public consultation, or legislative approval. The lack of opposition allows for a rapid implementation, as political manoeuvres, public protests, or legal challenges do not impede the implementation process. Authoritarian regimes can also swiftly adapt policies to changing circumstances due to a strong top-down control. They are not bound by lengthy legal processes, build-in checks and balances processes, or other procedures common to liberal democracies. The execution is more uniform and consistent across different regions and administrations, as the variability that might come from different regional/ local governments or political factions is severely reduced. The administrative machinery of the state is much more coordinated and synchronised, especially concerning large-scale projects and measures across various

sectors/ areas of responsibility. Dissent and the following negotiations with various interest groups are not slowing down the implementation process. Lastly, direct control over (social) media allows for control over information dissemination and leads to steering public perception effectively so that all parts of society are much more aligned with state directives and opinions, as this would be the case in liberal democracies.

The Indirect Approach and the Weaponisation of Economics

Several instruments for economic coercion can be identified, which can be clustered into means of the direct or indirect approach.

Direct Approach	Indirect Approach
Sanctions/ Embargoes	Partnerships/ Trade Relations
Currency/ Commodities Manipulation	Corporate Acquisitions
Debt Trap Diplomacy	Trade Policies
Tariffs	Investment and Aid
De-Coupling	Market Access
	De-Risking

Source: Author.

Numerous examples could be found to outline the Chinese approach in each category, but only selected cases will be taken to illustrate the multipronged strategy of coercion. The first example is the “One Belt, One Road”- or “Belt and Road-Initiative” (BRI). It was initially designed to secure land routes to the Indian Ocean and integrate the Eurasian regions into a Chinese-led economic sphere. Today it encompasses several other initiatives under the roof of the BRI (for example, activities in Africa, South America and the Polar region, to name a few).[39] Since the beginning, a volume of 1.053 trillion USD of cumulated investment has taken place.[40] It consists mainly of a land belt and a maritime road to Europe. As the PRC is currently heavily dependent on several maritime chokepoints, both for their resources-import and their trade-exports, developing a land-based alternative was evident.[41] At the same time, new markets could be opened for its growing surplus production.

Looking at the maritime dimension, the PRC follows a so-called ‘String of Pearls’ approach,[42] building a chain of seaports mirroring the Sea Lines of Communication from China to South Asia, South East Asia, the Middle East, parts of Africa and finally, Europe. Hungary may be the most prominent example of

how the PRC is looking for opportunities to get a foothold into the community of European countries. As the first European country to sign a BRI agreement, Hungary has already received at least 16 billion Euro Foreign Direct Investment, making it the primary destination for Chinese business. In addition, Hungary has recently received a loan from the PRC of 1 billion Euros. On the other side, Hungary used between 2016 and 2022 six times its veto power to block the EU Council's decisions against the PRC.[43] With the PRC partially mitigating the negative effect of Hungary's strained relationship with the EU, Hungary is becoming the PRC's bridgehead into Europe. Examples are the electric car manufacturing and battery production. But Hungary is also one of the main manufacturing and logistics hub for Chinese technology companies (e.g. Huawei). Looking at the current tariff conflict with the EU, such a bridgehead will help Chinese companies twofold. EU-imposed tariffs can be avoided more easily and the PRC can more easily continue to offload excess inventory to Europe and other countries to the extent of how domestic demand weakened. As a counter-measure to those tariffs, the PRC initiated an investigation into selected EU goods, such as, pork (one of Spain's biggest exports) and certain liquors (especially from France), in an effort to weaken European coherence. Another example would be Italy, which joined the BRI in 2019 but dropped out in 2023. In July 2024, however, a three-year action plan, including, for example, a cooperation agreement between Stellantis and Leapmotor on electric vehicles, was agreed upon. In summary, effects such as political capture through investment and aid policies as well as transforming a former nonexcludable and nonrival asset equally available to all commercial clients into a geopolitical token of the PRC of the BRI can be found.[44]

A second example is the use of trade/ export restrictions, especially with regard to critical materials, especially rare earths. In 2010, after an incident between the PRC and Japan,[45] the PRC imposed a two-month ban on exports of rare earths to Japan. In 2023, shortly after the restriction on semiconductor exports to the PRC, the PRC declared export restrictions on graphite products. This was followed immediately by another set of restrictions on germanium and gallium (both critical for the production of semiconductors). This happened after the Netherlands supported the U.S. restrictions (as the Dutch company ASML is the world leader in developing and manufacturing so-called photolithography machines necessary for the production of semiconductors. Recently, export restrictions were imposed on Antimony, without a clear incident as a trigger. It was only said that the export would be restricted in those cases where a country will use Chinese goods to undermine national sovereignty, security and interests. It has to be considered that it is not only so much the supply of the critical raw material itself, but the PRC has heavily invested in the refinery capacity as well. In graphite, for example, it refines more than 90 per cent of global supply.[46] It should also be considered that the

PRC is trying to control the whole value chain in critical sectors: it controls up to 80 per cent of all production steps for solar panels and 60 per cent of those for wind turbines and electric car batteries alike.

As a last example, the strategy of de-risking[47] can be highlighted, where the characteristics of liberal democracies with independent, self-determined economic actors showcase the vulnerability in economic warfare. Looking at the example of the U.S., where the so-called “Outbound Investment Order” was a necessary addition to the existing export control rules. While selling critical technologies directly to the PRC was banned, investors were still allowed to fund Chinese firms developing the same technologies. Open markets with only lightly limited market actors (companies, investors and consumers alike) can only be steered to a certain extent in the direction of a specific national security interest. The same phenomenon can be observed in Germany. As de-risking was an agreed European strategy,[48] it was strongly advocated in Germany in 2023 as well.[49] In 2024, no structural and long-lasting effect can be observed.[50] In summary, it can be concluded that political statements do not equal corporate actions. On the other side, in the PRC, with its authoritarian structures, it is much easier to achieve, as the reaction towards Japan in 2012 – after another incident[51]–showed. After the state-controlled press made the incident public, it was for the government only to manage the popular aversion against Japan by channelling the nationalistic feelings of individuals and companies (expressed, for example, in the boycotts of Japanese goods, cancellation of flights and holidays, etc.) in the wanted direction.

The Necessity to Adapt

To conclude, the PRC aims to enhance and execute geopolitical and geoeconomic power globally, and at the same time, challenges/weakens the existing international rule-based order to install an alternative, accommodating to a greater extent Chinese values and political beliefs: “That order would span a ‘zone of super-ordinate influence’ in Asia as well as ‘partial hegemony’ in swaths of the developing world that might gradually expand to encompass the world’s industrialised centres.”[52] This order would follow the idea of a “community of shared future for mankind” (official English translation)[53] or a “community of common destiny for mankind” (a more literal translation).[54] This order would damage liberal and democratic values, as “order abroad is often a reflection of order at home”. [55] The prominent example of the failed attempt of “One Country, Two Systems” is a likely projection of the future order with the PRC as an at least partial hegemon. Economic coercion, especially applied through mainly an indirect approach as the PRC does, against states whose economies rely mainly on the private sector, an integrated global supply chain system for their welfare, and an open society regarding the

spreading of information and media content, favors the authoritarian regime. Pluralistic welfare economies must adapt to maintain the escalation dominance—also in exchanges based on indirect approaches—against a monolithic party-state capitalism.

There are several approaches of how an adaption could look like. Liberal democracies might create multilateral anti-economic coercion measures. This could be, for example, the set-up of new or the strengthening of existing bi-, tri- or multilateral agreements, which could create a more unified and cohesive barrier against coercion. Several examples can be found or are under discussion. ‘Quad’ (U.S., India, Australia, Japan) has gained momentum, in which the economic dimension (for example, supply chain resilience) is a strong pillar, and it is already reaching out to other organisations for common ground, in particular looking towards the EU and ASEAN.[56] Existing partnerships, like those between the U.S. and Japan or the U.S. and Korea, have been strengthened,[57] and new ones forged (U.S., Japan, Philippines).[58] Unilateral actions can also be observed, taking, for example, India’s Act East Policy[59] (also nicknamed Necklace of Diamonds) and – under the umbrella of the “India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor”[60] – its agreement with Iran to develop Chabahar Port[61] on the mouth of Hormuz Strait as counter-encirclement strategies to the PRC’s String of Pearls approach. There are other initiatives (e.g. the EU Global Gateway Initiative,[62] the multinational Supply Chain Resilience Initiative,[63] and the G-7’s Build Back Better World Initiative[64]) out there to convince countries to seek financial resources from multilateral rather than Chinese providers. Other former decisions are under scrutiny for renewal. One example would be the “Trans-Pacific Partnership”.[65] When the U.S. left, not only was a chance to lower trade barriers lost, but it also deprived the U.S.—with the help of like-minded partners – of co-designing the rules governing trade in the Asia-Pacific region. As a kind of replacement, the “Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement”[66] without U.S. participation, sees the PRC with its trading power in a central role. Active participation in supranational, international, and regional organisations not only has a (geo)economic but also a geopolitical dimension in terms of connectivity and influence with a strong economic multiplier effect. Efforts are underway to compensate for this situation, for example, the “Indo-Pacific Economic Framework”[67] with its 14 members has achieved progress in one pillar (supply chains), but another important pillar (trade) still lacks decisive advancement. The discussion is also to establish some form of the 1994 abolished “Coordinating Committee for Multilateral Export Controls”, [68] but now with a more expansive view of national security – not only looking at goods that can be used for military purposes as it was done before but integrating economic concerns to a greater degree. The term “economic NATO”[69] could fit the intended purpose.

Another potential thread to explore could be the creation of reverse dependencies, as the PRC still has an export-driven economic growth model. Although the PRC is coming up to level playing fields in a lot of sectors and technologies, there are still areas where the Western world has market dominance. At the same time, the PRC's national capacities and capabilities are not up to the cutting-edge level for still some time. Failing imports in those areas can make the PRC hardly a substitute. There will always be a domestic impact for the restricting countries, sometimes quite high, as it is the case with the U.S. ban on semiconductor exports to China (U.S. Federal Reserve estimates costs of 130 billion USD in collateral damage).[70] It has to be considered, though, that the PRC is not only implementing its own de-risking- and indigenisation strategy (in which, for example "Made in China 2025" is part of it), but for the PRC, de-risking is not an economic goal; it is a political one, following a different logic from Western companies' strategies.

A last potential avenue to explore would be the creation of redundancies. Western liberal democracies and their economies depend on building as many trade relationships as possible, creating a possibility to hedge against unforeseen disruptions. That is true in the sense of infrastructure (as seen with the "Ever Given" in the Suez Canal and the necessity for rerouting due to the attacks of the Houthi in the Red Sea), but also for supply to meet demand. The model of frictionless, just-in-time supply chains with low inventories and stocks has to be scrutinised for geostrategic weaknesses. Such a strategy would be preemptive, both against inflationary shocks, abrupt decline in exports, and sudden decline in exports and other non-trade effects of geopolitics.

In the geopolitical and geoeconomic competition with the PRC, the indirect approach must be considered dead if it is unable to create a sufficient and balancing counter-effect to the PRC, which is using exactly the same kind of approach. Countering the indirect approach used by the PRC through direct means like sanctions (where the positive impact can be questioned anyway, seeing the sanctions against North Korea or lately Russia) or a full decoupling (with probably the same negative effect on GDP as it was the case due to the financial crisis or COVID-19), will probably deteriorate the fundamentals of our economic system. In addition, it remains questionable if the Western political systems and their societies at large would be able to survive this kind of competition.

Endnotes

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- [4] Based on the work of John Fuller and John Boyd.
- [5] Once again referring to the work of Liddell Hart.
- [6] C. Wu, "Dialectics and the study of Grand Strategy: A Chinese view," China Military Science, No. 3 2002, 144–145, <https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/CASI/Display/Article/2867621/itow-dialectics-and-the-study-of-grand-strategy-a-chinese-view/>.
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- [8] Political warfare was defined as "the employment of all the means at a nation's command, short of war, to achieve its national objectives". (G. F. Kennan, "The inauguration of organized political warfare," April 1948, <https://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/document/102805/download>); see also: W. R. Kintner, J. Z. Kornfeder, "The new frontier of war: Political Warfare, present and future," London 1963.
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factors have made it difficult for the military sphere to serve as the automatic dominant sphere in every war. War will be conducted in non-war spheres. If we want to have victory in future wars, we must be fully prepared intellectually for this scenario, that is, to be ready to carry out a war which, affecting all areas of life of the countries involved, may be conducted in a sphere not dominated by military actions." (Ibid., 169).

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- [32] C. Bi, “On the soft casualty in modern wars,” in: Chinese Military Science, No. 5 2003, 122-126; Y. Yao, Z. Mao, “Sun Tzu’s Art of War and mainstream contemporary Chinese theories of war,” in: Chinese Military Science, No. 6 2004, 9-13.
- [33] The definition of grey zone activities undertaken by China in this paper agrees with the following understanding: “Most definitions of the gray zone key on the uncertain political and operational space between war and peace; they describe calibrated coercion that does not breach certain escalatory thresholds while achieving certain coercive effects.” (I. B. Kardon, “Combating the Gray Zone: Examining Chinese threats to the maritime domain,” Testimony for the record before the House Committee on Homeland Security, Subcommittee on Transportation and Maritime Security, June 04, 2024, https://carnegie-production-assets.s3.amazonaws.com/static/files/2024.6.7%20Kardon%20CHS%20Testimony_rev.pdf).
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